

Influence of Matrix-Reinforcement Bond and Environmental Conditions on Properties of Fiber Reinforced PP Composites

G. Gianotti, A. Mula, P. Parrini

Istituto Guido Donegani S.p.A., Centro Ricerche, Novara, Via G. Fauser, 4, 28100 Novara, Italy

ABSTRACT

PP composites were prepared by extrusion with chopped strand glass fibers and by compression molding of PP with unidirectional oriented and random glass fibers; woven cloths with differential orientation resistance were also used.

Characterizations were performed by measuring static and dynamic fatigue strengths under various environmental temperature and humidity conditions.

The influence of fiber-matrix bond on ultimate properties of composites were analyzed.

Laboratory fatigue tests and experiments were determined in order to evaluate the ultimate functional effectiveness of composites in long-term service.

